

ON THE ART OF MUSIC IN TEACHING HISTORY LESSONS TO GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS METHODS AND METHODS OF USE OF RESOURCES

Zakirova Zilola Azamovna

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Senior teacher of the Department of Music Education

Abstract: This article deals with the art of music in the teaching of history lessons of general secondary schools. additional materials in explaining reality to students data used as and this data on the basis of didactic aspects of educating young students in an aesthetic spirit are explained.

Key words: music, troupe, musical instrument, style, song, composer, conservatory, score, lesson, practice, exhibition, tradition.

Today, the influence of the science of history in educating the young generation as a perfect person is increasing. History science not only forms students' skills and competences about our past, but also makes the young generation patriotic, in his formation as a hardworking, spiritually perfect person also has its own place. Especially in the conditions of today's globalization, the information conveyed to the minds of students through history textbooks is also important in protecting the minds of young people from mass cultural threats.

History teaches students about our country's social, political, not only providing information about their economic life it also plays an important role in raising their cultural level. Today, every nation and state is in its past with how much he contributed to human civilization wants to be proud. In addition, what are the important aspects of human civilization? inculcating the wealth of their ancestors in the younger generation not only creates feelings of national pride and pride in them but also in educating the young generation in moral and aesthetic spirit is an important factor. Approaching the issue from this point of view history

is unique in providing spiritual education to young people We are sure once again that there is a place. In the criteria of the formation of human civilization, urbanization, architecture, the traditions of religion, art and statehood are important.

In this article, we are dealing with cultural life in the process of teaching history lessons to students of general education schools we try to explain the methods and recommendations of using music related resources and materials in explaining related topics.

We know that music dates back to the primitive days of mankind is considered one of the first discoveries. For example Primitive people, when some danger approaches them, or if they invite each other to somewhere, hit something and make a sound and sent a "signal" to his relatives. Also to ensure the success of the hunt, to chase away evil spirits It is also related to the fact that in performing archaic rituals related to the sound of hitting something against something, dancing in front of the fire in a manner analogous to that primitive music the teacher used certain attributes to explain the aspects to the students. General secondary education schools Amir Temur from the history of Uzbekistan explains to his students the topic of the "founder of the state" centered on Amir Bio near Termiz by Temurga Piri Sayyid Baraka tug (flag) and tabl (drum), which are symbols of the state in the village the drum is not only a musical instrument but also one of the symbols of the state and that it is one of the recognized attributes record and reflect this information in the 6th grade on the Ayritom friez It can also be explained in connection with the statue of musicians [3].

Also, while explaining to the students of the 7th grade the topic of cultural life in Movoraunnahr and Khorasan in the beginning of the 9th-13th centuries, the art of music in our country was also great during this period. That he made progress, holidays, weddings, national elections and that other ceremonies were certainly not without melody and song should be noted. During this period, musicians played oud, tanbur, kobiz, rubob, flute, trumpet, trumpet, neighbor, law

and many others like that a wide range of string, percussion and wind instruments along with mentioning that he used this instrument pictures of the tools or the original condition of the tool shows itself, not only will students' interest in this topic increase, but also the opportunity to try playing these words passion also appears. During coverage of this topic the teacher should also give information about "Shoshmaqom" formed on the basis of folk tunes. Then "Shoshmaqom" is a classic song of the Uzbek and Tajik peoples by explaining to students the culture of these two peoples, noting that history and traditions are also common will have to pass.

In this place, the art of music is poetry and musicology it should be noted that it developed along with science. In addition, Abu Nasr Farabi, who received the title of "second teacher", dedicated to music a separate "Book of Music" It will be useful to explain to the students that he wrote a treatise [5]. General secondary education schools While teaching 7th graders about our national culture, especially the history of music, together with "Shosh Makom" It is appropriate to note that there are Khorezm statues as well as Fergana, Bukhara and Khorezm roads of status execution. Especially the fact that the art of status has developed significantly in the years of independence, the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018, the Maqom Festival was organized in Samarkand by noting that it was done to further enrich their ideas about art and the status and interest in its performance can be increased [6].

Also in Movoraunnahr and Khorasan, Timur and the Timurids that culture and art developed rapidly during the period in the context of the explanation of the culture of the Eastern Renaissance, that is The first renaissance of the 9th-12th centuries and the 14th-15th centuries if you give information about the second renaissance, Uzbekistan Readers of the content and essence of the third renaissance promoted by the President of the Republic Sh. Mirziyoev it becomes somewhat easier to bring to mind. During the lesson XIV-XV new tunes and songs, musical instruments and the creation of rare works on music theory, too there are many

skilled musicians, musicians and hafiz it is also appropriate to note that it has come out. Abduqadir Nayi, Qulmuhammad Shaikhi, Hasan Udiy, Shahquli Gijjaki, Qasim, who lived and worked in this period It is necessary to explain the names of the lords [7].

In this period, along with skilled musicians, thinkers and poets such as Ulug'bek, Navoi, Jami, Binoi also played music. Engaged in art, to a certain extent to its development It is also useful to remind readers that they have contributed besides, the Sultan of Movoraunnahr, the great astrologer and scientist Mirzo Ulug'bek finished five treatises dedicated to music, as well as "Buluji", "Shodiyona", "Akhloqi", He created the tunes "Tabrizi", "Usuli Ravan" and "Usuli otlig".if it is mentioned that they did, the scope of the students' knowledge expands further. Alisher Navoi, who played an important role in the cultural life of the 14th and 15th centuries and was a major representative of classic Uzbek literature, was nicknamed "Navo", which means "tune" with music. Alisher Navoi by noting that it is related it is possible to achieve a further increase of interest in students' creativity. At this point, Alisher Navoi himself is a skilled musician It can be mentioned that the song "Isfakhani" was created by Alisher Navoi. Moreover, Abdurahman Jami and the great artists of this period Kamoliddin Binayylar created a work on the theory of music, a new development in connection with music and poetry it should be noted that it has been raised to the stage.

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